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Heavy Flavour Spectroscopy

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Abstract

The discovery of hadronic states beyond the conventional two-quark meson and three-quark baryon picture in the last two decades is one of the most amazing accomplishments in fundamental physics research. We review the experimental progress on the study of the exotic states (also known as the XYZ particles) beyond the conventional quark model. We give a general review and then focus on the lineshape measurement of the $X(3872)$, observation of new decay modes of the $Y(4230)$ and new vector charmoniumlike states $Y(4500)$ and $Y(4790)$, evidence for the neutral isospin partners of the charged charmoniumlike Z_{cs} states, discoveries of the tetraquark state candidates with four different flavours or two-pairs of charm-anticharm quarks and the pentaquark states.

Introduction: Hadron spectroscopy is a field of frequent discoveries and surprises, and the theoretical difficulties in understanding the strong interaction in the color-confinement regime make the field even more fascinating. The tremendous data collected by the BaBar, Belle, BESIII, LHCb, and other experiments and improved theoretical tools developed to analyze the experimental data result in rapid progress of the field.

In the conventional quark model, mesons are composed of one quark and one anti-quark, while baryons are composed of three quarks. However, many quarkoniumlike states were discovered at two B -factories BaBar and Belle [1] in the first decade of the 21st century. Whereas some of these are good candidates of quarkonium states, many other states have exotic properties, which may indicate that exotic states, such as multi-quark state, hadronic molecule, or hybrid, have been observed [2].

BaBar and Belle experiments finished their data taking in 2008 and 2010, respectively, and the data are still used for various physics analyses. BESIII [3] and LHCb [4] experiments started data taking and contributed to the study of exotic hadrons since 2008. Most of the discoveries of the such states were made at these four experiments.

Figure 1 shows the history of the discovery of some of the new hadrons, started from the observation of the $X(3872)$ in 2003 [5]. In this article, we present recent experimental progress and focus on those states with exotic properties, including the $X(3872)$, $Y(4260)$, $Z_c(3900)$, P_c and their siblings.

Figure 1: Discovery of some heavy exotic states from experiments.

The lineshape of the $X(3872)$: The $X(3872)$ was observed in 2003 by the Belle experiment [5], and confirmed very soon by the CDF [6] and $D0$ [7] experiments in $p\bar{p}$ collision.

The mass of the $X(3872)$ has been measured as 3871.65 ± 0.06 MeV [8], which is lower than the mass threshold of $\bar{D}^0 D^{*0}$, 3871.69 ± 0.11 MeV, by 0.04 ± 0.12 MeV, to be compared with the bounding energy of the deuteron of 2.2 MeV.

The width measurements are less precise and model dependent since the $X(3872)$ is very narrow and the mass resolution of the experiments is usually much larger than the intrinsic width. Fitting the $\pi^+\pi^-J/\psi$ invariant mass distribution with a Breit-Wigner (BW) function, LHCb reported a width of about 1 MeV (the mass resolution is 2.4–3.0 MeV); and the fit with a Flatté function with constraints from other measurements yields a FWHM of 0.22 MeV which depends strongly on the $X(3872) \rightarrow \bar{D}^0 D^{*0}$ coupling [9, 10].

Although the statistics are low at BESIII experiment, the high efficiencies of reconstructing all the $X(3872)$ decays modes and the very good mass resolution in the $\bar{D}^0 D^{*0}$ mode (< 1 MeV) make it possible to measure the lineshape of the $X(3872)$ state. BESIII determined the pole locations of the $X(3872)$ based on a simultaneous fit to the data samples of $X(3872) \rightarrow D^0 \bar{D}^0 \pi^0$ and $X(3872) \rightarrow$

$\pi^+\pi^-J/\psi$, with the $X(3872)$ produced in $e^+e^- \rightarrow \gamma X(3872)$ process [11]. The parameterization of the $X(3872)$ lineshape, with the effect of D^{*0} width taken into account, is developed in Ref. [12]. The fit results and the lineshape of the $X(3872)$ are shown in Fig. 2. The lineshape parameters are determined to be $g = (0.16 \pm 0.10_{-0.11}^{+1.12})$, $\Gamma_0 = (2.67 \pm 1.77_{-0.82}^{+8.01})$ MeV and $M_X = (3871.63 \pm 0.13_{-0.05}^{+0.06})$ MeV. Here g denotes the effective coupling constant of the $X(3872)$ to neutral and charged $D^*\bar{D}$; the constant Γ_0 represents all the channels except $D^*\bar{D}$, and is separated into three parts: $\Gamma_0 = \Gamma_{\pi^+\pi^-J/\psi} + \Gamma_{\text{known}} + \Gamma_{\text{unknown}}$; and M_X is the mass of the $X(3872)$. The FWHM of the lineshape is determined to be $(0.44_{-0.35}^{+0.13} \text{ } ^{+0.38}_{-0.25})$ MeV. Two poles are found on the first and second Riemann sheets corresponding to the $D^{*0}\bar{D}^0$ branch cut. The pole location on the first sheet is much closer to the $D^{*0}\bar{D}^0$ threshold than the other, and is determined to be $(7.04 \pm 0.15_{-0.08}^{+0.07})$ MeV above the $D^0\bar{D}^0\pi^0$ threshold with an imaginary part $(-0.19 \pm 0.08_{-0.19}^{+0.14})$ MeV.

Figure 2: The fit to the $D^0\bar{D}^0\pi^0$ (left) and $\pi^+\pi^-J/\psi$ (middle) invariant mass distributions. Data are taken from Ref. [11]. The $X(3872)$ lineshape at the best estimation is shown in right panel. The vertical dashed line indicates the position of $D^{*0}\bar{D}^0$ threshold.

Belle measured the $X(3872)$ lineshape with $B \rightarrow X(3872)K \rightarrow D^0\bar{D}^{*0}K$ [13]. The peak near the threshold in the $D^0\bar{D}^{*0}$ invariant mass spectrum is fitted using a relativistic BW function. Belle determined a mass of $(3873.71_{-0.50}^{+0.56} \pm 0.13)$ MeV and a width of $(5.2_{-1.5}^{+2.2} \pm 0.4)$ MeV. The peak is also studied using a Flatté lineshape and the lower limit on the DD^* coupling constant g is determined to be 0.075 at 95% credibility. A coupled channel analysis of the data used in this analysis and those in $X(3872) \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-J/\psi$ decay is highly recommended to get reliable information about the $X(3872)$ lineshape.

Observation of new $\psi(4230)$ decays and new vector states $Y(4500)$ and $Y(4790)$: The Y states were discovered in the initial state radiation in the B -factory experiments, and they have $J^{PC} = 1^{--}$. So these state can also be produced directly in e^+e^- annihilation experiment like BESIII. Much improved measurements of the $Y(4260)$ [14], $Y(4360)$, $Y(4660)$ [15] and so on are achieved, their new decay modes are discovered and new vector states are observed.

The most precise measurements of the $Y(4260)$ are from the BESIII experiment [16, 17]. By doing a high luminosity energy scan in the vicinity of the $Y(4260)$, BESIII found the peak of the $Y(4260)$ is much lower (so it is now named the $\psi(4230)$) than that from previous measurements and the width is narrow, and there is a high mass shoulder with a mass of 4.32 GeV if fitted with a BW function. Since then, more new decay modes of the $\psi(4230)$ were observed including $\pi^+\pi^-h_c$ [18], $\pi^+\pi^-\psi(2S)$ [19], $\omega\chi_{c0}$ [20], $\pi\bar{D}D^* + c.c.$ [21], $\pi\bar{D}^*D^*$ [22], and $K\bar{K}J/\psi$ [23, 24].

The cross sections of $e^+e^- \rightarrow K^+K^-J/\psi$ at center-of-mass energies from 4.127 to 4.600 GeV are measured based on 15.6 fb^{-1} data collected by the BESIII experiment [23]. Two resonant structures are observed in the line shape of the cross sections. The mass and width of the first structure are measured to be $4225.3 \pm$

2.3 ± 21.5 MeV and $(72.9 \pm 6.1 \pm 30.8)$ MeV, respectively. They are consistent with those of the established $\psi(4230)$. The second structure is observed for the first time with a statistical significance greater than 8σ , denoted as $Y(4500)$. Its mass and width are determined to be $4484.7 \pm 13.3 \pm 24.1$ MeV and $111.1 \pm 30.1 \pm 15.2$ MeV, respectively. This state is confirmed in $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi\bar{D}^*D^*$ reported in Ref. [22].

With the world's largest e^+e^- scan data sample between 4.226 and 4.95 GeV accumulated by BESIII, the Born cross sections of $e^+e^- \rightarrow D_s^{*+}D_s^{*-}$ are measured precisely [25]. Besides two enhancements in the energy dependent cross sections at around 4.2 and 4.45 GeV that may come from the $\psi(4160)$ or $\psi(4230)$ and the $\psi(4415)$, respectively, a third resonance structure ($Y(4790)$) is observed at around 4.7~4.8 GeV with statistical significance greater than 6.1σ . Due to the limited number of data points around 4.79 GeV, the fitted mass of the third structure varies from 4786 to 4793 MeV and the width from 27 to 60 MeV. This could be the same state observed in $e^+e^- \rightarrow K_S^0 K_S^0 J/\psi$ with a statistical significance of 4.0σ [24].

In the charmonium energy region between 3 and 5 GeV, we now have identified 6 well known ψ peaks (J/ψ , $\psi(2S)$, $\psi(3770)$, $\psi(4040)$, $\psi(4160)$, and $\psi(4415)$) and 9 new Y structures ($Y(4230)$, $Y(4320)$, $Y(4360)$, $Y(4390)$, $Y(4500)$, $Y(4630)$, $Y(4660)$, $Y(4710)$, and $Y(4790)$). They are all vector states and they cannot be all charmonium states. While more experimental efforts are needed to resolve the origins of these states, theoretical efforts are also necessary to identify if the vector charmonium hybrids and/or tetraquark states have already been observed.

Neutral partners of charged charmoniumlike Z_{cs} states: The charged charmoniumlike state $Z_c(3900)$ discovered in $\pi J/\psi$ by the BESIII [26] and Belle [27] experiments, the $Z_c(4020)$ discovered in πh_c by the BESIII [28] experiment, and the $Z_c(4430)$ discovered in $\pi\psi(2S)$ by the Belle [29] experiment are all states with minimal quark content of $c\bar{c}u\bar{d}$.

Recent studies try to search for states with one of the four quarks replaced by a different quark, for example, the Z_{cs} states with quark content $c\bar{c}u\bar{s}$. BESIII announced observation of a near-threshold structure $Z_{cs}(3985)$ in the K^+ recoil-mass spectra in $e^+e^- \rightarrow K^+(D_s^- D^{*0} + D_s^{*-} D^0)$ [30] with a mass of 3983 MeV and a width of about 10 MeV; and LHCb reported two resonances decaying into $K^\pm J/\psi$, the $Z_{cs}(4000)$ with a mass of 4003 MeV and a width of about 131 MeV, and the $Z_{cs}(4220)$ with a mass of 4216 MeV and a width of about 233 MeV [31]. The widths of the $Z_{cs}(3985)$ and $Z_{cs}(4000)$ are quite different, maybe one of them is the strange partner of the $Z_c(3900)$ with the d quark replaced with an s quark. Both BESIII [32] and LHCb [33] reported evidence for the neutral partners of the Z_{cs} states at around 4 GeV with quark content $c\bar{c}u\bar{s}$. These indicate that these states form isospin doublets.

The $Z_c(3900)$ ($Z_c(4020)$) and Z_{cs} states may form multiplets shown in Fig. 3, the missing states can be searched for with the existing or future data samples.

New tetraquark states from LHC experiments: LHCb experiment observed two new resonances with four different flavors with mass of $2908 \pm 11 \pm 20$ MeV and width of $136 \pm 23 \pm 13$ MeV, which decay to $D_s^+ \pi^+$ and $D_s^+ \pi^-$, respectively, from a combined amplitude analysis for the decays $B^0 \rightarrow \bar{D}^0 D_s^+ \pi^-$ and $B^+ \rightarrow D^- D_s^+ \pi^+$, which are related by isospin symmetry. The former state indicates the first observation of a doubly charged open-charm tetraquark state with minimal quark content $c\bar{s}u\bar{d}$, and the latter state is a neutral tetraquark composed of $c\bar{s}u\bar{d}$ quarks ($T_{c\bar{s}}$). Both states are found to have spin-parity 0^+ , and their resonant parameters are consistent with each other, which suggests that they belong to an isospin triplet [34].

Tetraquark states $T_{c\bar{s}}$ with four different flavors ($c\bar{s}u\bar{d}$) have been search for at

Figure 3: The possible multiplets of the $Z_c(3900)$ and $Z_c(4020)$.

LHCb and evidence (3.9σ) for two states ($X_0(2900)$ and $X_1(2900)$) in D^-K^+ system were reported from a PWA of $B^+ \rightarrow D^+D^-K^+$ events by the LHCb experiment [35]. They are good candidates for the flavour partners of the $T_{c\bar{s}}$ states, and more flavour partners with other quark contents and spin-parities are expected.

The LHCb, ATLAS, and CMS experiments reported observation of states decay to two charmonium states [36, 37, 38]. The $X(6900)$ is observed in all these three experiments, and a new structure ($X(6600)$), with a significance above 5σ , and evidence for another new structure ($X(7300)$), with a local significance of 4.1σ , are found at CMS. The masses, widths, and significances are obtained in model-dependent ways without considering possible interference between the resonances. These are good candidates for tetraquark states with two pairs of charm-anticharm quarks.

Pentaquark states: In the decay of $\Lambda_b \rightarrow J/\psi p K^-$ analyzed by the LHCb experiments, there are three very narrow peaks in the invariant mass distribution of $J/\psi p$ [39]. In a simple fit to the invariant mass spectrum, the resonance parameters of the $P_c(4312)^+$, $P_c(4440)^+$, and $P_c(4457)^+$ are determined. They are all narrow, and the $P_c(4312)^+$ state peaks right below the $\Sigma_c^+ \bar{D}^0$ threshold, the $P_c(4457)^+$ state peaks right below the $\Sigma_c^+ \bar{D}^{*0}$ threshold, while the $P_c(4440)^+$ state peaks about 20 MeV below it.

Being so close to the thresholds, they are very good candidates for the molecules of a charmed baryon and an anti-charmed meson, and more similar states close to the other baryon-meson thresholds are expected. In a following amplitude analysis of $B \rightarrow J/\psi \Lambda \bar{p}$ decays, a narrow resonance in the $J/\psi \Lambda$ system, consistent with a pentaquark candidate with strangeness, is observed with high significance [40]. The mass and the width of this new state are measured to be $4338.2 \pm 0.7 \pm 0.4$ MeV and $7.0 \pm 1.2 \pm 1.3$ MeV, respectively. It is very close to the $\Xi_c^+ D^-$ threshold of 4337.4 MeV. Evidence for states at around $\Xi_c^0 \bar{D}^{*0}$ threshold are reported in Ref. [41].

Summary and Perspectives: Many states with exotic properties were observed in the past two decades. Some of them are quite close to the thresholds of two heavy objects, either two heavy flavor mesons or one heavy flavor meson and one heavy flavor baryon, like the $X(3872)$ ($\bar{D}^0 D^{*0}$), $Y(4220)$ ($D_s^{*+} D_s^{*-}$ or $\bar{D} D_1$), $Z_c(3900)^+$ ($\bar{D}^0 D^{*+}$), $Z_c(4020)^+$ ($\bar{D}^{*0} D^{*+}$), Z_{cs}^+ ($\bar{D}^0 D_s^{*+}$), $P_c(4312)^+$ ($\Sigma_c^+ \bar{D}^0$), $P_c(4440)^+$ and $P_c(4457)^+$ ($\Sigma_c^+ \bar{D}^{*0}$); and some other states are not close to such thresholds, such as the $Y(4360)$, $Y(4660)$, $Z_c(4430)^+$, and $Z_{cs}(4220)^+$. These may suggest that we did observe the hadronic molecules close to thresholds and we also observed hadronic states with some other quark configurations like compact tetraquark states and so on. It is expected that more results will be produced by the Belle II, BESIII, LHCb, and other experiments.

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